

Comparison Of Direct Trocar Insertion Versus Needle In Creation Of Pneumoperitoneum In Patients Undergoing Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy has become a routinely used procedure for surgical removal of gall bladder in patients of Cholelithiasis. To minimize access related trauma, several techniques, numerous instruments, and multiple approaches have been introduced during the last century. These include the Veress pneumoperitoneum- trocar for "classic" or closed entry, the open (Hasson) technique, direct trocar insertion without prior pneumoperitoneum, use of shielded disposable trocars Direct trocar insertion (DTI) and veress needle insertion (VNI) techniques are the most common laparoscopic entry techniques. Objective: The objective of study is to compare the number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum using Veress Needle and Direct Trocar insertion in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Study Design: Randomized Controlled Trial. Settings: Department of General Surgery, Bolan Medical Complex Hospital Quetta. Duration of study: 19-Dec-2019 to 18-Jun-2020. Patients and Methods: A total 188 patients with diagnosis of Cholelithiasis and planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy having age 30-75 years of both genders were included. In all patients detailed history, followed by complete routine examination and baseline investigations were done. Patients were divided into two groups, Group A (Direct trocar entry), Group B (Veress Needle). All patients were kept in ward till clinically stabilized and management protocol was observed for all included patients. Results: Mean age of patients was 46.23±11.28 years included in this study. Mean body mass index (BMI) was 25.10±3.34 kg/m². There were 108 (57.45%) females and 80 (42.55%) male patients. Successful creation of pneumoperitoneum in first attempt was done in 120 (63.83%), second attempt in 45 (23.94%) patients and in third attempt in 23 (12.23%) patients. successful creation of pneumoperitoneum in first attempt was done in 69 (73.40%) patients in DTI group and in 51 (54.30%) in VNI group. While pneumo-peritoneum was created in second attempt in 16 (17.00%) patients in DTI group and in 29 (30.90%) patients in VNI group. Pneumo-peritoneum was created in third attempt in 09 (9.60%) patients in DTI group and in 14 (14.80%) patients in VNI group with p-value of 0.023. Conclusion: Direct trocar insertion (DTI) is a safe and quick technique for creation of pneumoperitoneum. Pneumoperitoneum can be successfully created in first attempt in higher number of patients in DTI group as compared to veress needle insertion (VNI).

Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy has become a routinely used procedure for surgical removal of gall bladder in patients of Cholelithiasis. Abdominal access is the first step of laparoscopic surgery for creating a pneumo-peritoneum, and this part includes the first risky step of visceral and abdominal wall injuries as well. This abdominal access is associated with some unique complications, which are extremely rare with open surgery. Common complications include surgical emphysema, haemorrhage, bowel perforation, and vascular injuries.^{1,2}

To minimize access related trauma, several techniques, numerous instruments, and multiple approaches have been introduced during the last century. These include the Veress pneumoperitoneum- trocar for "classic" or closed entry, the open (Hasson) technique, direct trocar insertion without prior pneumoperitoneum, use of shielded disposable trocars Direct trocar insertion (DTI) and veress needle insertion (VNI) techniques are the most common laparoscopic entry techniques. Each of above mentioned access instrument enjoys preference by individual surgeon, according to training and easy availability.³⁻⁵

In a Canadian study constituting 407 obstetricians and gynecologists, most of them always established pneumoperitoneum prior to insertion of the primary trocar. Furthermore, among them, few had encountered vascular or organ injury attributable to the Veress needle insertion 25.6% and 15.0% experienced vessel or organ injury from the primary and secondary trocars, respectively *these authors concluded that number of attempts can be a factor in increasing number of complications at first attempt complication rate was 0.8%-16% at 2nd attempt 16.31%-37.5% at more than three attempt 86%-100%*.⁶

A study conducted by Ertugrul et al. found significantly less number of attempts required to create pneumo-peritoneum in patients with direct trocar entry as compared to VNI group. The authors reported successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum in first attempt in 74.3% patients in DTI group and in 54.7% in VNI group. While pneumoperitoneum was created in 2nd attempt in 15.4% patients in DTI group and in 30.9% patients in VNI group.⁷

Several studies have compared the outcomes of DTI and VNI in patients undergoing laparoscopic procedures but only few studies have reported number of attempts in

both of these groups.⁷⁻⁹ So the purpose of this study is to compare number of attempts for successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum in patients undergoing laparoscopic procedure.

Rationale of study is to determine whether direct trocar entry or Veress needle is the easy access for creation of pneumoperitoneum with least number of attempts, as increasing number of attempts tend to increase the rate of complications, hence decrease safety of the procedure.¹⁰ So adopting a technique with higher first attempt success rate can help to reduce complications rate in patients laparoscopy cholecystectomy.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE SELECTION:

Inclusion criteria:

- Patient with diagnosis of Cholelithiasis and planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy.
- Having age 30-75 years
- both male and female genders were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patient with history of Advanced GI or Gynecological procedure.
- Chronic liver disease detected on Ultrasound abdomen and with coexisting deranged Liver function tests (bilirubin >1.1, AST, ALT > 45IU, Serum Albumin <3.3), ischemic heart disease (evident on ECG in form of Q waves).
- Previous laparotomy as it presented with difficulty in creation of pneumoperitoneum due to intra-abdominal adhesions.

The above mentioned condition may act as a confounder and introduce bias in the study results.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

After approval of synopsis, 188 patients meeting the inclusion criteria were included in the study. A written informed consent was taken from all patients before including them in this study.

In all patients detailed history, followed by complete routine examination and baseline investigations were done.

Patients were divided into two groups, Group A (Direct trocar entry), Group B (Veress Needle). Patients were randomly divided via lottery method either to undergo laparoscopic procedures to establish pneumoperitoneum with Veress needle or Direct Trocar entry.

All procedures were performed by General Surgery specialist having postgraduate qualification such as (FCPS FRCS FACS MS and minimum 3 years' experience after post-graduation) in Surgery and have performed more than 50 laparoscopic procedures in a year.

Insertion into the abdomen was made with patients in a 20⁰-degree Trendelenburg position, the abdominal wall elevated with towel clamps and the tip of the trocar was turned 30⁰ degrees towards the pelvis at supra umbilical fold and veress needle at 45⁰. All trocars and veress needle used were disposable, with a safety shield. Maximum 3 attempts was made and in case of failure open technique was used. All patients were kept in ward till clinically stabilized and management protocol was observed for all included patients. All the above mentioned information including demographic features were recorded on a pre-designed proforma. Strictly exclusion criteria was followed to control confounders and bias in the study results. All the gathered information was noted on a Pre-designed Proforma (Annexure-I).

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE:

Data will be analyzed in SPSS v23. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for numerical variables like age and BMI.

Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables like gender, number of attempts full successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum.

Chi-square test was applied to compare number of attempts for creating pneumoperitoneum in direct trocar insertion group and Veress needle group and pvalue ≤ 0.05 was considered as significant difference.

Data was stratified for age, gender, BMI to address effect modifiers. Post stratification

Chi square test was applied with p value ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Mean age of patients was 46.23 ± 11.28 years. Minimum age was 30 years and maximum age was 75 years (Table 1).

Mean height was 161.95 ± 10.27 cm. Minimum height was 139.00 cm and maximum height was 190.00 cm. Mean weight of patients was 65.54 ± 11.14 kgs. Minimum weight was 40 kgs and maximum weight was 90 kgs. Mean body mass index (BMI) was 25.10 ± 3.34 kg/m². Minimum BMI was 18.40 kg/m² and maximum BMI was 34.68 kg/m² (Table 2).

There were more female as compared to male patients. There were 108 (57.45%) female and 80 (42.55%) male patients (Figure 1).

Successful creation of pneumoperitoneum in first attempt was done in 120 (63.83%), second attempt in 45 (23.94%) patients and in third attempt in 23 (12.23%) patients (Figure 2).

On comparison of number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum between the groups, successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum in first attempt was done in 69 (73.40%) patients in DTI group and in 51 (54.30%) in VNI group. While pneumo-peritoneum was created in second attempt in 16 (17.00%) patients in DTI group and in 29 (30.90%) patients in VNI group. Pneumo-peritoneum was created in third attempt in 09 (9.60%) patients in DTI group and in 14 (14.80%) patients in VNI group. This difference was statistically significant with p-value of 0.023 (Table 3). Stratification of age was performed, in age groups 30-44 years, successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum in first attempt was done in 57 patients in DTI group and in 16 patients in VNI group. While pneumo-peritoneum was created in second attempt in 04 patients in DTI group and in 07 patients in VNI group. Pneumo-peritoneum was created in third attempt in no patient in DTI group and in 09 patients in VNI group. This difference was statistically significant with p-value of <0.001 . In patients having age

45-75 years, successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum was done in first attempt in 12 patients in DTI group and in 35 patients in VNI group. While pneumo-peritoneum was created in second attempt in 12 patients in DTI group and in 22 patients in VNI group. Pneumo-peritoneum was created in third attempt in 09 patients in DTI group and in 05 patients in VNI group. This difference was also statistically significant with p-value of <0.028 (Table 4).

Stratification was also performed on the basis of gender and BMI, there was also strong association was found of these variables with number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum between the groups.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of age.

Age (Years)	
Mean	46.23
S.D.	11.28
Minimum	30
Maximum	75

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of Height, Weight and Body Mass Index (BMI).

	Height (cm)	Weight (Kg)	BMI (Kg/m ²)
Mean	161.95	65.54	25.10
S.D.	10.27	11.14	3.34
Minimum	139	40	18.40
Maximum	190	90	34.68

Figure 1. Frequency of gender.

Figure 2. Frequency of number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum.

Table 3. Comparison of number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum between the groups.

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups		P-value
	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	
1	69 (73.40%)	51 (54.30%)	0.023

2	16 (17.00%)	29 (30.90%)	
3	09 (9.60%)	14 (14.80%)	

Table 4. Stratification of age to determine the association of age with number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum between the groups.

(Age Group = 30-44 Years)

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups		P-value
	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	
1	57	16	<0.001
2	04	07	
3	0	09	

(Age Group = 45-75 Years)

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups		P-value
	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	

1	12	35	0.028
2	12	22	
3	09	05	

Table 5. Stratification of gender to determine the association of gender with number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum between the groups.

(Gender = Male)

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups		P-value
	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	
1	61	05	<0.001
2	05	09	
3	0	0	

(Gender = Female)

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups	P-value

	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	
1	08	46	0.030
2	11	20	
3	09	14	

Table 6. Stratification of BMI to determine the association of BMI with number of attempts for successful creation of pneumoperitoneum between the groups.

(BMI \leq 24.99 Kg/m²)

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups		P-value
	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	
1	33	28	0.353
2	08	14	
3	06	07	

(BMI \geq 25.0 Kg/m²)

Number of Attempts for Successful Creation of Pneumoperitoneum	Groups		P-value
	Group A (Direct Trocar Entry)	Group B (Veress Needle)	
1	36	23	0.038
2	08	15	
3	03	07	

DISCUSSION:

Almost half of the complications of laparoscopic surgery occur during entry into the abdomen.^{11, 12} Debates on the safety of laparoscopic surgery generally focus primarily on procedure-specific complications, such as biliary injury in laparoscopic cholecystectomy, and secondarily non-biliary injury, i.e. vascular or enteric injuries caused by the main procedure. Access-related injuries are usually evaluated in separate studies; major vessel or bowel injuries caused by entry are as infrequent as 0.1 -0.4%.¹³ It has been reported that 83% of vascular injuries, 75% of bowel injuries, and 50% of local haemorrhage injuries were caused during primary trocar insertion.¹⁴ It is anecdotal, but very possibly true, that these complications are underreported, especially as the minor complications related to entry have minimal impact on the overall outcome.

Increasingly more general surgeons and gynaecologists are using the DTI technique in laparoscopic surgery. The increase in its use is principally due to the fact that there are fewer complications, both major and minor, with this procedure, and it is likely to become the technique of choice in the near future.

Today, the Veress Needle (VN) is the commonest peritoneal access method. In a survey of laparoscopy entry techniques practiced by gynaecologists, it emerged that 90% use a closed needle technique, 8% a direct entry technique without a pneumoperitoneum, and 1% opt for the open method. More interestingly, over half said that they would not alter their preferred technique even for obese patients or those who had undergone previous abdominal surgery. Only one third admitted that their techniques had changed in the past five years. VN-related bowel injury is reported to be 0.3-0.8 /1000 and for open entry it is 0.6-2.8 /1000.¹⁵ These studies include both low and high-risk cases and are obviously biased against the open technique which is usually reserved for the latter subset. When only prospective and randomized studies are collated, DTI has a statistically significant lower incidence of bowel injury as compared to other techniques (1.9/1000 for VN, 1.5/1000 for open and 0.3 / 1000 for DTI).^{16,17}

In an open comparative randomized prospective study on the feasibility and safety of DTI versus the VN technique in 598 non-obese patients, minor complications were nil in the DTI group and 5.9% in the VN group in the form of 3.4% of subcutaneous emphysema and 2.5% of extraperitoneal insufflation. Major complications were nil in the DTI group and 1.3% among VN patients; the authors concluded that in thin patients with no more than one previous abdominal operation, DTI is a safe alternative to the VN technique and is associated with fewer minor complications, whereas there is no difference between the two techniques as regards major complications.¹⁸ In a metaanalysis of 18,577 cases of direct trocar entry, no

major vascular injury was reported as compared with 0.04% for Veress needle entry.¹⁹ In studies by various authors, no major injuries related with trocar placement were observed using the DTI technique but significantly more minor injuries were documented with the VNI technique.²⁰

Number of attempts for creating pneumoperitoneum is a very important determinant of complications of laparoscopic procedures. So in present study we determined that which technique requires minimum number of attempts and the needle can be successfully inserted in first attempt. In present study, successful creation of pneumoperitoneum in first attempt was done in 69 (73.40%) patients in DTI group and in 51 (54.30%) in VNI group. While pneumo-peritoneum was created in second attempt in 16 (17.00%) patients in DTI group and in 29 (30.90%) patients in VNI group. Pneumoperitoneum was created in third attempt in 09 (9.60%) patients in DTI group and in 14 (14.80%) patients in VNI group.

Our study results are similar to the results of the study conducted by Ertugrul et al., who found significantly less number of attempts required to create pneumoperitoneum in patients with direct trocar entry as compared to VNI group. The authors reported successful creation of pneumo-peritoneum in first attempt in 74.3% patients in DTI group and in 54.7% in VNI group. While pneumo-peritoneum was created in 2nd attempt in 15.4% patients in DTI group and in 30.9% patients in VNI group.⁷

The major limitation of present study is that we only focused on successful creation of pneumoperitoneum and did not focused on the complications of these procedures. So there is a need to conduct large randomized controlled trials to determine the safety of these entry techniques.

CONCLUSION

Direct trocar insertion (DTI) is a safe and quick technique for creation of pneumoperitoneum. Pneumoperitoneum can be successfully created in first attempt in higher number of patients in DTI group as compared to veress needle insertion (VNI).

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